

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D3.1 Methodological report (1)

Qualitative and collaborative data collection

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CoS	Community of Schools
NEET	Not in Employment, Education or Training
PAR	Participatory Action Research
ECEC	Early Childhood Education and Care
FG	Focus Groups
ST	Safe Teaching
BG	Bulgaria
IT	Italy
PO	Poland
PT	Portugal
SP	Spain
LT	Lithuania

Executive Summary

This deliverable contains the methodological report with the results of qualitative research carried out in six European countries (Spain, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Bulgaria, and Lithuania), focusing on the 'Safe Education' model.

Through in-depth interviews, life stories with young NEETs, focus groups and collaborative observations with teachers, the emotional needs of children and young people, barriers to educational inclusion and the skills needed to build safe school environments were explored. The research, based on the Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology, involved more than 150 participants and has enabled the development and validation of practical tools such as the 'Safe Teaching Observation Tool' and the 'Teacher's Workbook'.

The findings highlight that family factors, emotional stability at home and teacher support are key to preventing school dropout. The experiences of NEETs reveal trajectories marked by emotional insecurity, family violence, forced migration or poverty, but also show the transformative potential of second chance schools. In the case of teachers, there is a clear need for continuous training, conflict resolution protocols, decent working conditions and institutional support to promote pedagogical relationships based on trust, empathy and inclusion. The Safe Education model makes sense when the entire educational community collaborates in a structured and context-sensitive manner.

Finally, the report highlights the urgent need for systemic reforms that guarantee specialised human resources, culturally adapted inclusion strategies and sustained investment in teacher well-being. Despite differences between countries, there is general agreement on the need to strengthen cooperation between families, schools and administrations. The proposals put forward point to an educational transformation based on the recognition of diversity, the reduction of class sizes, collaborative work, training in social and emotional skills, and the design of education policies that are sensitive to context and equity.

1. Introduction

This report contains the results of the analysis carried out on the activities included in Tasks 3.1 and 3.2:

T3.1 Qualitative data collection and analysis:

In-depth interviews with families with children enrolled in ECEC and/or primary education located in the communities represented in the LET'S CARE CoS.

Life stories with NEETs enrolled in second-chance schools.

Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders at the local level (within CoS) and national level.

Interviews with policymakers.

T3.2 Qualitative and collaborative data collection with teachers:

Focus groups with approx. 4-10 teachers per school (in the LET'S CARE CoS), for identifying key Safe Teaching (ST) competencies, barriers, and facilitators.

Design of the Safe Teaching self/peer-observation tool using the focus groups' findings in the form of a validation grid.

Self/peer observation of teachers (some of the teachers who participated in the FG), with the aim of testing the self/peer observation tool and analysing their practice in terms of ST.

Applying these different methodological tools has significantly contributed to developing the "Safe Education Theoretical Model" (see D2.3. for reference).

The core objective of all the techniques applied is to understand children's needs and how their social contexts care for them. These techniques tackle our objective through the speech of the NEETs (life stories), the families (in-depth interviews), the teachers (focus groups), the educational communities and key actors influencing educational contexts (semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and policymakers).

In total, **more than 150 people** from families, NEETs, stakeholders, policymakers and teachers have been involved among the interviews, life stories, focus groups and teachers' self/peer-observations conducted¹.

2. Methodological framework

The **PAR² approach** is the umbrella theoretical approach framing the other methodologies applied (Lewin, 1946, 1973; Fals-Borda et al., 1972, 1985, 1999). As discussed under D1.2 and D1.3, co-creation is a central issue in the LET'S CARE project. Co-creation under the umbrella of the PAR approach ensures that the research is not only participatory but also deeply rooted in the principles of shared knowledge creation and ownership.

The process followed for the development of the research is presented in Figure 1 in Annex III. The co-creation process began by setting up an initial space where an idea could be proposed, refined, enhanced, rejected, or replaced by a new idea, leading to its final realisation and execution. Then, a preliminary meeting took place with the fieldwork teams from the partner organisations (BG, SP, IT,

¹ For detailed information on the profiles see Annex I.

² Participatory (collaboration through participation; empowerment of participants); Action (change in real life experience, evidence in terms of different outcomes) and Research (new knowledge, documented lessons).

LT, PO, PT) to exchange perspectives and collaborate on the design for implementation. The purpose was to go over the project's goals and explore the most effective methods for achieving them. For example, in the case of life stories with NEETs, the technique chosen was Photovoice, as it was considered the most appropriate to achieve the objectives. In the follow-up meetings and presentation of results, the fieldwork teams also transferred to the driving group the value that the participants themselves saw in the use of that particular technique, so that the choice of the best techniques to apply was the result of a co-creation in the methodological process. Once the best methodological tool to use had been decided, the CIDALIA and PROMAESTRO teams prepared tailored dossiers for each activity. For the development of the interviews and photovoice fieldwork, the dossiers included guidelines on the specific methodology (Dossier A) and the technical implementation and reporting (Dossier B). In the case of the FG and the observation process with teachers, there were three dossiers: the Focus Group dossier (for facilitators), the Teachers dossier (for observation), and the Facilitator dossier (for observation)³. The next step was to share the dossiers with the partners and to carry out training sessions about the techniques to be used (at least one training session per technique). From there, the partners carried out the fieldwork. At this stage, follow-up iterative meetings were held to supervise the final implementation and suggest better courses of action to achieve the goals.

2.1. Techniques' selection

The selection of the best tools and procedural approach was discussed and agreed upon based on the following criteria:

- *Alignment with research objectives*: the techniques should allow for tackling the research pillars and educational disengagement, underachievement and drop-out.
- *Flexibility and responsiveness*: the techniques should be standardised methods that allow adaptability to address contextual needs with cultural sensitivity.
- *Generativity*: The techniques should allow participants to be part of the knowledge co-creation.

Table 1 below presents the final selection of methodological tools or techniques.

³ The complete dossiers can be consulted in Annex II.

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 Table 1. Summary of methods

AIMS & RESEARCH QUESTIONS	SAMPLING SELECTION CRITERIA	RESEARCH PILLAR FOCUS & PARTICIPANTS	INSTRUMENTS & MATERIALS	ANALYTIC APPROACH
In-depth interviews with families				
<p>Aim: theoretical model development</p> <p>Research questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are the family's relationships with the child and the school? • What is their direct experience with institutions when dealing with underachievement or disengagement? 	<p><u>Inclusion criteria:</u> sufficient information condition → meets outcome criteria and any source of disadvantage. caregivers of children who underachieve at school, are disengaged or have dropped out + meet any axis of disadvantage/inequality key for the project aims (Ethnicity -especially Roma children migrant background (low) SES (Dis)ability (Non)parental care)</p> <p><u>Comparability and variability:</u> families whose children are doing well in school (maximum 1), but who have inequity variables</p>	<p>Pillar 1 – families and children</p> <p>24 families – 4 per country (BG, SP, IT, LT, PO, PT)</p>	<p>Dossier A: manual training on conceptualisation, sample selection and procedures for preparing and conducting the interviews</p> <p>Dossier B: manual training with implementation materials including introduction letters, interview script, standardised reporting template and information and consent templates</p>	<p>Systemic thematic analysis with <i>Dedoose</i>, an open-source thematic analysis software</p>
Photovoice Life stories with NEETs				
<p>Aim: theoretical model development</p> <p>Research questions:</p>	<p><u>Inclusion criteria:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants must be NEETs with a personal 	<p>Pillar 1 – children</p> <p>13 NEETs – 2 per country (BG, SP, LT, PO, PT) except in</p>	<p>Dossier A: manual training on conceptualisation, sample selection and procedures for preparing and conducting the interviews</p>	<p>Combination of sociological discursive analysis with visual analysis</p>

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do NEET youth construct and express their personal experiences of educational exclusion and reintegration? • What subjective meanings do NEETs attribute to their life events, as revealed through image-based dialogue? • How do gender, age, migratory status, and country influence their personal narratives of NEET youth regarding ESL? 	<p>history of exclusion and/or reintegration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willingness to provide self-taken photographs and engage in a reflective interview about them. • Ability to articulate personal experiences and meanings through both visual and verbal expression. 	<p>Italy, where three NEETs have participated</p>	<p>Dossier B: manual training with implementation materials including introduction letters, interview script, standardised reporting template and information and consent templates</p>	
<p>Semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and policymakers</p>				
<p>Aim: theoretical model refinement</p> <p>Research questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the opinions of politicians and different key actors on educational exclusion and social 	<p><u>Inclusion criteria:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders in or influencing in educational communities (NGO's, School principals, School boards, educational institutions and informal educational institutions, 	<p>Pillar 1 – children</p> <p>12 stakeholders – 2 per country (BG, SP, IT, LT, PO, PT)</p>	<p>Dossier A: manual training on conceptualisation, sample selection and procedures for preparing and conducting the interviews</p> <p>Dossier B: manual training with implementation materials including introduction letters, interview</p>	<p>Systemic thematic analysis with Dedoose open-source thematic analysis software</p>

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<p>connection of children in their community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the problems and the barriers that exist to eliminating educational exclusion? • How children’s relationships with schools and communities are related to low performance or lack of engagement. • What are stakeholders’ and policymakers’ proposals on the best ways to create a safe school at all four levels? 	<p>Community centres for children and youth, Neighbourhood associations)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers at different levels of administration 	<p>13 policymakers – 2 per country (BG, SP, LT, PO, PT) except in Italy, where three have participated</p>	<p>script, standardised reporting template and information and consent templates</p>	
Focus groups with teachers				
<p>Aim: theoretical model development Research questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What challenges and supports do teachers encounter in their teaching practices? 	<p><u>Inclusion criteria:</u> Teachers in the CoS’ centres at ECEC, primary or secondary level, rural or urban settings and both public and private ownership.</p>	<p>Pillar 2 - Teacher-student relationship</p> <p>90 teachers – 2 FG per country except in Bulgaria (3 FG), total participants: 18 BG,</p>	<p>Manual training on conceptualisation, procedures for preparing and conducting the focus groups, guidelines for accomplishing ethical and legal requisites, standardised reporting template and</p>	<p>Content analysis</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which factors define or shape a safe teaching practice? 		19 SP, 15 IT, 10 LT, 15 PO, 13 PT	information and consent templates	
Classroom observations				
<p>Aim: tools development</p> <p>Research questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What practices and interactions observed in the classroom contribute to or hinder a safe teaching environment, as perceived by teachers themselves and their peers? What insights into safe teaching practices emerge from systematic classroom observation among teachers? 	<p><u>Inclusion criteria:</u> Teachers in the CoS' centres at ECEC, primary or secondary level, rural or urban settings and both public and private ownership.</p>	<p>Pillar 2 - Teacher-student relationship</p> <p>62 teachers – 11 BG, 12 SP, 12 IT, 10 LT, 14 PO, 3 PT</p>	<p>Manual training for facilitators with guidelines (on conceptualisation, self-peer observation implementation procedures, ethical and legal requisites) and materials (reflection tools, evaluation questionnaire, workbook for teachers, self-peer observation rubric)</p> <p>Manual training for teachers with materials (reflection tools, evaluation questionnaire, workbook for teachers, self-peer observation rubric and golden rules of peer observation)</p>	Content analysis

Interviews are one of the paramount tools of qualitative methodologies, a technique designed to explore in detail the experiences, perceptions, values, and meanings that people attribute to certain phenomena. In-depth and semi-structured interviews enable a deep and contextualised understanding of social reality. It is a relaxed and trusting conversation in which the interviewees will delve into their experiences, opinions, values and motivations in a broad sense. The choice of this methodological tool in LET'S CARE is due to the efficient and environmentally friendly results it provides, which have allowed us to address our research questions in a convenient way and daily for the interviewees.

The photovoice technique is a participatory research and action methodology that uses the creation of images to prompt the participants' reflection. In the Photovoice method, participants use cameras to record environments or situations and generate data, thus becoming directly involved in the research process. The photographs speak of the visions and concerns of the NEETs, capturing their personal and collective reflections and points of view. This is because we are going to see through their eyes, a material that will serve as a perfect counterpoint to the discourse that emerged in the interview. Photovoice is based on certain criteria that make it a very powerful tool in terms of research and action:

- **Inclusive:** Participants feel challenged and active as part of the research and the discussions that take place through it.
- **Collaborative:** The technique can favour contact and links between people, generating collective knowledge and new synergies that can generate other, more practical inputs.
- **Representative:** In several of the photovoice applications around the world, marginalised or underrepresented communities have found a platform to express their perspectives and needs.
- **Generator of critical thinking:** The process generates the motivation for critical and analytical thinking in the participants.
- **Empowering:** Photovoice enables individuals to capture their lived experiences, stories and environments through photographs.
- **Meaningful learning:** Participants feel involved and capable of generating knowledge, resulting in highly relevant learning.
- **Approachable and fun:** The technique is a very pleasant way of dealing with young people, especially with those not used to group discussions or expressing their thoughts, as well as in cases of shyness or social anxiety. The technique easily creates a bond with the participant and bridges social and cultural distances. It can also be more entertaining than an interview, where we can be more passive.
- **Visual literacy:** Building on the participants' skills, the technique also helps to develop communication and the use of images for personal expression.

- **For young people**, it will be much easier to begin to express thoughts and feelings about their particular history through the images they themselves have taken. Through their discourse about them, we will gain access to their subjectivity, to the social representations about their community, or to the meanings they attribute to the events of their lives.

For us, it is a method of accessing the subjectivity of young people, useful for our analysis, and at the same time generating a process of self-awareness and empowerment. This leads us to a reflection, and that is that the real product of the Photovoice technique is not, as it might seem, in the photographs. The photographs taken become central elements to be later textualised and analysed through the development of processes based on dialogue, reflection, criticism and intersubjectivity. The photographs become central elements that later must be textualised and analysed through dialogue, and that intersubjective encounter between interviewer and interviewee (see Figure 4 in Annex III). Therefore, the potential of this technique is centred on its ability to generate discourse, to serve as a tool for reflection and discourse production. When a photo is textualised, it is an opportunity for individual reflection in the form of dialogue, expression, structuring and articulation of ideas. This promotes an alternative mode of communication through the fusion of images and words, an opportunity to narrate one's own life. It is interesting to remember that this technique also has great potential in pedagogical terms, due to its ability to create transformative and meaningful educational experiences for students.

Focus Groups are a qualitative research technique designed to explore collective experiences, social dynamics, and shared meanings within specific communities. In LET'S CARE, they served as a space for dialogic exchange among teachers, allowing them to express, contrast, and build perspectives on ST practices within their school contexts. The process began with the preparation and delivery of materials, along with training for facilitators in each country. Facilitators then recruited teacher participants from the selected schools.

During fieldwork, focus groups were held in each participating school, following a semi-structured discussion format and recorded for later analysis. The group setting fostered a sense of mutual recognition and co-construction, enabling teachers to reflect on their values, challenges, and practices in a shared space. The transcripts were subsequently analysed using content analysis methodology, and the most salient themes were categorised. These emerging ideas became the foundation for developing two observation tools central to the next research phase: the Safe Teaching Observation Tool, used for direct classroom observations, and the Pedagogical Reflection Tool, designed to assess school culture and the involvement of different educational stakeholders.

In essence, the focus groups acted as a collective lens through which to understand the pedagogical landscape of each context, identifying common concerns, successful strategies, and areas for improvement. The collective voices of teachers provided rich insight into the lived realities of ST and contributed directly to the co-construction of instruments for further exploration.

Classroom Observation is a qualitative technique that allows for the direct and situated exploration of teaching practices. In LET'S CARE, it played a dual role: both as a tool for empirical data collection and as a catalyst for reflective practice among teachers. The observation process was grounded in the idea that seeing one's own teaching — or that of a colleague — through a structured and safe lens can be a powerful source of learning and transformation.

The process began with training sessions and the distribution of detailed materials to facilitators and teachers. Facilitators then guided the observation phase, offering support and tutoring throughout. Teachers engaged in both peer observation and self-observation using the Safe Teaching Observation Tool, which helped them to notice, describe, and reflect on elements of their own pedagogical practices related to safety, inclusion, and emotional climate.

Each observation cycle culminated in a guided reflection session using the Pedagogical Reflection Tool, encouraging teachers to interpret their observations in light of broader school culture and community dynamics. These sessions created spaces for collaborative learning and professional dialogue. Teachers also compiled their insights in an individual Teacher's Workbook, where they documented their reflections, discoveries, and new questions emerging from the process.

The observation tools were validated through two iterative rounds of feedback: first by the teachers themselves, and then by the National Coordinators' Board. Their suggestions led to improvements in both the tools and the accompanying guidelines, reinforcing the participatory and responsive nature of the methodology.

Ultimately, classroom observation in LET'S CARE was not merely about assessing what happens in class; it was a structured opportunity for teachers to pause, observe, and reframe their practice — fostering a culture of pedagogical awareness and continuous improvement.

The protocols, instruments and standardised reporting materials of the selected techniques are available in Annex II.

2.2. Reliability, validity and methodological challenges

To ensure methodological consistency and data **reliability** across countries, the research teams implemented standardised procedures, supported by comprehensive training materials and interview guides (Dossiers A & B). These resources were instrumental in reducing interviewer bias, thanks to the structured preparation of national teams and the training provided to the designated group (DG) responsible for implementation. Furthermore, the centralisation of coding and analysis within the leading team contributed to enhanced procedural reliability and comparability of findings.

In terms of **validity**, the depth and richness of the qualitative data substantially reinforce construct validity, offering detailed insight into participants' lived experiences. The variability across national contexts, alongside efforts to reach discourse saturation, strengthens internal validity by ensuring

thematic robustness. The intentional inclusion of diverse participant profiles, including those experiencing and not experiencing educational disadvantage, enhances external validity and supports meaningful comparative analysis. The overall research design promotes both construct and ecological validity, being deeply rooted in real-world educational contexts and aligned with the study’s theoretical goals. The use of triangulation across methods and participant groups further strengthens the validity of the conclusions drawn.

Despite these strengths, the research also faced several **methodological challenges**. Cross-country differences in educational systems, policy frameworks, and socio-cultural environments introduce significant complexity in both data collection and interpretation. Moreover, language and cultural differences may influence both participant expression and researcher understanding, underscoring the need for linguistic sensitivity and contextual awareness. These challenges highlight the importance of a careful, context-sensitive synthesis during the theoretical model-building phase, ensuring that the resulting frameworks are robust, inclusive, and empirically grounded in the diversity of experiences captured throughout the study. Table 2. Presents the specific ways in which each technique has provided reliability and validity to the results, together with the methodological challenges experienced in each case.

Table 2. Methodological specifications by technique

RELIABILITY	VALIDITY	METHODOLOGICAL CHALLENGES
In-depth interviews with families		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardised procedures across countries, supported by training materials and interview guides (Dossiers A&B) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to subjective meanings and emotions that are difficult to capture through surveys or other structured methods. Flexible format that allows questions to be adapted and explored in greater depth based on the responses, enriching the content. Contextualisation of experiences within the interviewee's social, cultural and emotional environment, facilitating a deeper interpretation. Building trust through empathetic conversation, which 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing clear and comfortable communication is key to the success of an in-depth interview, as it seeks to create a bond that facilitates the expression of ideas and allows for an understanding of the interviewee's experience. Qualitative interviews require careful preparation; therefore, a protocol has been developed to guide the conversation according to the research objectives. It is essential to ask open-ended questions and avoid

	<p>encourages honest expression on sensitive topics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful for exploring complex phenomena linked to symbolic, identity, cultural or emotional dimensions, such as emotional security in schools. 	<p>closed questions, as the latter limit responses and hinder reflection and the recall of experiences.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Example of the difference: closed question: 'Do families participate in school life?' / open question: 'How do families participate in school life?'
Photovoice life stories with NEETs		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardised procedures across countries, supported by training materials and interview guides (Dossiers A&B) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High ecological validity from co-constructed stories. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visual narratives add interpretative depth but reduce consistency. Differing expressive abilities affect output quality. Requires researcher reflexivity to avoid over-interpretation.
Semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and policymakers		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardised procedures across countries, supported by training materials and interview guides (Dossiers A&B) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to qualified and professional information. It provides insights into high-level technical and institutional dimensions, something that is difficult to obtain through surveys or other structured methods. Flexibility and adaptability. The open format allows the interviewer to adapt questions and dig deeper based on the answers, which enriches the content and allows for the discovery of aspects that were not initially anticipated. Trust. By establishing an empathetic conversation, the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing clear and comfortable communication is crucial in an in-depth interview, as building a close bond helps elicit the interviewee's personal ideas, experiences and points of view. Thorough preparation is essential for qualitative interviews; an interview protocol has been developed to guide the conversation according to the research objective. Open-ended questions are preferred, as closed questions limit detailed

	<p>interviewee often feels more comfortable talking honestly about sensitive issues, which improves the quality of the information.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploration of complex phenomena. They are particularly useful for studying topics that involve symbolic, identity, cultural or emotional dimensions, such as the emotional and relational determinants affecting students' feelings of security as a root cause of underachievement, disengagement, and dropout. 	<p>responses; open questions encourage explanation, reflection, and memory recall.</p>
Focus groups with teachers		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data consistency may vary depending on facilitator skill and group dynamics. • Recurrent themes across groups increase dependability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High construct validity through shared, interactive reflection. • Group interaction reveals tacit knowledge and nuanced perspectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of groupthink or conformity bias, especially in hierarchical contexts. • Time-consuming transcription and nuanced interpretation are needed.
Classroom observations		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised tools and training improve inter-observer reliability. • Self-observations can introduce subjective variability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong content validity from direct observation of real practice. • Reflective sessions increase internal validity through triangulation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The observer effect may alter natural behaviour. • Limited observation time may not capture the full classroom complexity.

3. Main results

This section briefly presents the results obtained across the views of each targeted group of participants that contributed to shaping the Safe Education theoretical model.

3.1. Pillar 1: children and family relationships

FAMILIES

In the case of **families**, the focus of the discussion has been on their own experience and life trajectory, through which we have addressed our objectives: to understand the specific perceptions and situations related to safe education, as well as the barriers and promoting factors that families encounter in practice.

Families (parents and legal guardians) are a group that occupies a fundamental social position between children, schools and communities. *A large majority (approximately 70%) of the families interviewed state that their children are highly satisfied with the school⁴.* Parents associate their children's satisfaction with school with words like those seen in the cloud in Figure 2 of Annexe III. *Approximately 30% of the families interviewed state that their children are unhappy with school.* Among the main reasons they point out⁵, the lack of friendships at school on the part of their child is remarked as affecting their overall experience. They also point to the lack of continuity in teaching staff from year to year, making it difficult for teachers to get to know the children well enough to treat them in a motivating way.

Another concern is the *lack of solutions provided by schools* to address problems as they arise. Some families report negative experiences, explaining that they perceive the school as unwilling to help parents solve their children's problems or improve the well-being of students. In their view, the school does not support vulnerable children or those who need extra help, but rather shifts the responsibility to parents and external counselling centres. Moreover, they express frustration that the school does not offer any activities for parents and only contacts them to discuss parenting problems. Finally, *some teachers are seen as behaving unprofessionally*, which families attribute to burnout, dissatisfaction with their jobs, or a lack of enjoyment in working with children (Verbatim #FAMILY, 4, IT).

NEETs

In the case of **NEETs**⁶, the focus of the discussion has been on the consequences of dropping out of school on a social and psychological level, for the integration of the individual into society and for his or her general well-being.

It is interesting to note that it is not the economic situation that most concerns the participants, in terms of how it may have been affected by their broken school career. *The experience of*

⁴ See verbatims #FAMILY, 2, SP; #FAMILY, 4, BG; #FAMILY, 4, IT in Table 4, Annex I

⁵ See verbatims #FAMILY, 2, BG; #FAMILY, 4, PL in Table 4, Annex I.

⁶ See Table 5 in Annex I: Examples of verbatim quotes from NEETs Photovoice.

consequences is much more holistic, understood as "consequences in life in general". Concerns could be clustered more around a concern for social integration. The fear derived from expulsion from the school system has more to do with a fear of social exclusion (Verbatim #Female, Italy, 3).

The data show that we should see *dropping out of school as a point and a continuation*, a point that comes from a trajectory, and that opens the way to another stage. Dropping out of school appears as a very important event in the lives of the participants, a moment of discomfort and deep uncertainty, in which they have to face pain and a lot of frustration (Verbatim #Female, Lithuania, 2). The photographs show that in the case of those who are still in a situation of family insecurity, it is places such as school, or even the street, which make them feel safer. Being safe at home reflects good family ties, a sign of stability in the immediate circle. The *need for their own spaces* has been pointed out in the youngest children, who are still in their adolescence: spaces where they are not disturbed by parents, tutors or siblings.

Economic vulnerability arises as a key factor in school dropout. Financial hardship and situations of homelessness often act as triggers, while *migration may be the cause of school dropout*. Migration is a phenomenon that, in the cases explored, has fractured students' lives in various ways. Some NEET participants tell us how they dropped out of school because their family often changed their place of residence or because they had nowhere to live. In this situation, some participants stop going to school because they do not have the minimum conditions to do so. The value that the family places on the school and the attention it gives to the child are two variables that, if they are low, directly influence the possibility of dropping out of school (Verbatim #Male, Portugal, 2; #Female, Poland, 2).

Stability and security at home emerge as key factors for academic performance. NEET Participants frequently mentioned the breakdown of the family unit, and, above all, problems associated with behaviour and addictions. We have also found stories of violence with very harmful results for the participants. *Silence* has been a significant element in discussions about the family; it operates directly in the conversation as a sign that, most probably, serious facts are hidden or that it is still too hard to talk about it. Finally, *spending long hours on the street* is frequently linked to school difficulties or discomfort at home, highlighting the importance of being listened to and having one's own space.

TEACHERS

Teachers⁷ point out that *families have an important role in facilitating ST*, first and foremost by creating a home environment where the basic needs of students are covered. *It is crucial that families have a positive attitude towards school life and trust and support teachers and other school specialists* in pursuit of common goals regarding their child's learning and development. In their views of their child's learning, they should accept mistakes as part of the process, avoid exerting excessive pressure

⁷ See Table 19 in Annex I: Examples of quotes from teachers participating in the Focus Groups and observations.

for academic results, and encourage autonomy and taking responsibility for one's own learning. With respect to their *involvement in school*, they should attend meetings regularly when required and collaborate in activities when they are invited to do so.

STAKEHOLDERS AND POLICYMAKERS

Concerning the question of how the family reality affects school results in academic and relational terms, **stakeholders & policy makers**⁸ pointed to a range of factors that shape this connection. In this context, and more generally, it is highlighted that *families tend to focus on supporting their children's academic success as a pathway to professional success*. This is often accompanied by the intention to inspire children to follow in the footsteps of other family members. When families have a close relationship with school and get involved in activities and opportunities at school, children tend to have better development and learn more effectively. The participants' experience is that *families are usually open to collaborating with the school when difficulties arise*, and this collaborative work is essential to overcome difficulties and improve academic engagement. In line, stability at home contributes significantly to better learning and getting better grades at school.

Most *families are well informed*, and if not, they seek information. They support their children, communicate positively with the school, and trust its work and pedagogical strategies. However, some families have difficulties understanding that their children have different aims in life/professional goals, and this can lead to *divergences in dealing with children's expectations*. Moreover, *some parents are more absent because of work*; in some situations, the school context can substitute, in terms of support, for families that are not so available to monitor students' school trajectory.

Stakeholders & policy makers also pointed out that family reality greatly affects academic and coexistence results. A high percentage of pupils who come from *dysfunctional or socio-educationally disadvantaged families* repeat a year and/or end up leaving the education system prematurely. It can also be observed that some of these pupils have coexistence and relationship problems. A current challenge for developing teacher-student relationships and feelings of belonging is the *multiculturalism of the schools*; some teachers also come from other countries.

Other challenges are the economic disadvantages and disparities between students. Due to a shortage of teachers, some may lack pedagogical training, only having received training on the subject they are teaching. They highlight that schools must recognise the diversity of families nowadays. *Schools need to try different strategies* and, if they do not work, analyse the problem from a social perspective instead of just thinking that parents have faults, they are lazy and don't want to commit to the school, because sometimes the strategies that schools are using are not the most

⁸ See Table 6 in Annex I: Examples of verbatim quotes from stakeholders & policy makers interviews.

adequate. A strategy that needs to be used nowadays is using AI tools such as translators on the phone to be able to communicate with families, as the identity, culture and language conditions are barriers to school-family relationships. Lastly, parents, students, local communities, and other stakeholders already contribute to school governance through participation in the General Council of schools, where some important decisions are made.

Regarding the question of the impact of gender on experiences and success or dropout, there are divergent views. On the one hand, *most interviewed people believe that gender and school success or dropout are not directly associated*. Usually, they say that what influences dropout is students' maturity, which is highly associated with age. In this sense, they stress that boys can have more challenges because they are less mature than girls at an early age, specifically in the transition from childhood to adolescence. On the other hand, *a minority mentioned that the impact of gender is important*. Girls tend to be more successful in their educational experiences in primary school. Then in secondary school, the drop-out rate is even more pronounced among boys, although if we look at the ethnic minorities, it is girls who drop out of the education system earlier. A special case is that of Roma students. They are more affected by socioeconomic vulnerabilities, situations of social and cultural exclusion, as well as discriminatory experiences. From the first to the fourth grade, gender does not influence school success or dropout. However, in the upper grades, there are reported cases where segregation and family poverty influence girls to drop out due to early marriages, and older boys go to work to help financially and feed their large families.

3.2. Pillar 2: teacher-student relationships

FAMILIES

Although the vast majority of **families** state that their children are satisfied with the school, their perception is that the *school's teachers' actions to promote security and resolve conflict situations are not satisfactory*. Less than half of the families interviewed responded satisfactorily to this question (Verbatim #Family, 2, SP).

Concerning the actions that the teachers can take to promote security, the following *good practices* are noted. There is a standard procedure for conflict resolution in the school (Verbatim #Family, 4, PL). Teachers receive continuous training in subjects such as active listening, dialogue, conflict management, and the expression of emotions. They introduce working methods, such as projects, that are engaging. Moreover, the school maintains constant communication with families, providing abundant information and taking their opinions into account. Finally, personalised attention to students helps prevent conflicts.

The families who state that they do not feel satisfied with the teacher's actions in terms of *generating a safe environment and conflict management* consider it essential to *involve families* in conflict

resolution⁹. They also highlight that teachers lack protocols for managing conflicts, which makes effective intervention difficult. In addition, they note that stressful situations at school affect not only the ability to learn but, more importantly, the willingness to learn. Ultimately, some families perceive that the teachers' response to conflictive situations is to lower students' grades.

NEETs

This perspective contrasts with the **NEETs'** one, who consider *teachers as key figures of authority, protection and support*: having a good or bad teacher is understood by the participants as a direct cause of their success or dropout. The participants showed very radical attachments and detachments. The teacher, social worker or trusted mediator can be vital for school success, just as a bad authority figure can have dire consequences for the child or adolescent.

TEACHERS

When asked about defining ST, the **teachers** remarked on practices that encourage collaboration, open communication and personalisation of teaching and learning processes. *ST practices* teach students to respect and appreciate the opinions of others so that they can share their thoughts and feelings without fear of being judged. Among its benefits, participants agree that establishing a secure bond with their students is critical to their emotional well-being and educational success. ST creates spaces that provide physical and psychological safety, characterised by trust, acceptance, and protection. These spaces nurture students' personalities and foster their personal development. ST also develops social and emotional skills, such as acceptance of mistakes as learning opportunities, conflict resolution, empathy and effective communication. Pupils feel that their needs are recognised and that they can freely share their successes and failures.

A classroom climate that facilitates ST is defined by motivation, trust and respect between teachers and pupils. Students can express their emotions and needs in the classroom, and the teacher acknowledges their opinions and rhythms. On the other hand, situations in the classroom that prevent a ST are related to students' low motivation to learn, the manifestation of disruptive behaviour and negative perceptions of the teacher.

In this context, teacher participants point out that the *teacher's actions* facilitate ST when treating all students equally and paying attention to their tone of voice and the language they employ when communicating with students. In maintaining classroom discipline, they try to strike a balance between closeness and seriousness and respond consistently and coherently to established school protocols when students break the rules. The teacher seeks to hold students accountable for their learning and behaviour and reinforce the students' positive behaviour and attitudes.

⁹ See main issues in verbatims #FAMILY, 4, BG; #FAMILY, 2, LT; #FAMILY, 3, LT; #FAMILY, 4, LT in Table 5, Annex I.

Teachers practise ST when they create an atmosphere of trust and promote integration and collaboration. They do this by helping students identify their emotions, encouraging empathy, respect and helping dispositions, and providing opportunities to resolve conflicts when they arise. They display motivation and a positive attitude towards teaching despite the difficulties encountered, and during the lesson, they seek to foster student motivation as well. Finally, it should be noted that the teacher who facilitates ST acts as a point of reference for their students, showing that they are available when needed, instilling confidence, and working collaboratively with other teachers in the school.

Concerning the *structure and delivery of lessons*, the participating teachers gave several recommendations to take ST into account when planning lessons. At the outset of the lesson, teachers can provide an explanation of the sequence and objectives of the lesson and incorporate opening dynamics that awaken the interest and attention of the students. In the lesson, there should be times when socialising learning and collaborative work are encouraged and, in turn, spaces for autonomous work when required. In addition, it would be ideal for teachers to provide breaks and spaces for students to express themselves and be heard. In terms of activities, it is important to use different resources and methodologies, always taking into account the students' interests and adapting activities and lesson dynamics to students' abilities and needs. Teachers should promote student participation and a culture of error, where mistakes are accepted and understood as part of the learning process. This is important to maintain the students' self-esteem and academic self-concept.

Regarding *the role of the teacher as a tutor*, ST translates into aiming to attend to individual students' needs and creating spaces for communication with students outside as well as inside the classroom. In order to do this, teachers need to have sufficient time for tutoring actions in their working day. In terms of communication with families, ST means holding individualised meetings to discuss the students' progress and difficulties and inviting families to participate in a variety of school activities. In terms of the professional community, it is necessary for the tutor to share information and collaborate with other teachers and specialists at the school to ensure the best care.

Lastly, concerning *teachers' perceptions and needs in relation to the ST*, the teachers express that, when implementing ST, they experience positive emotions as a result of strengthening bonds with other members of the educational community, including motivation, gratitude, satisfaction with their work and confidence in their abilities. On the other hand, when they encounter difficulties related to the bonding dimension, they feel insecure and anxious, as they feel unable to meet the needs and expectations of learners. Moreover, they may feel misunderstood or undervalued by other members of the educational community, which leads to frustration and discouragement. Despite this, teachers persevere and draw strength from the support of their colleagues.

3.3. Pillars 3-4: school climate and safe education

FAMILIES

From the **families'** perspective, a positive school climate is shaped by several interconnected factors that influence both the learning environment and school outcomes. At the core is the school climate, which the families define as calm, respectful and inclusive. *Teachers play a central role* in shaping this atmosphere by interacting with students in a composed and understanding manner. Rather than shouting, they speak to students calmly and engage them in open conversations about their problems. This respectful communication fosters trust and emotional safety. Families also emphasise that *schools should feel interesting and engaging to students* (Verbatim #Family, 3, IT), which contributes to a more motivated and involved learner.

Another fundamental element of a positive climate is the social environment. Families value a *peaceful school setting* where insults or hostility are absent, and where students of all ethnic backgrounds are treated with tolerance and respect. A welcoming classroom culture, in which students behave in friendly and inclusive ways and teachers help maintain a supportive microclimate, is seen as essential. Equally important is the perception that the school acts as a close-knit, friendly community (Verbatim #Family, 2, SP), where all students, regardless of their individual difficulties, are fully included (Verbatim #Family, 3, LT). *Inclusion* is not seen as optional but as a necessary feature of an equitable and healthy school.

When students experience academic difficulties, families tend to respond with emotionally supportive and proactive strategies. They report using *empathy-based approaches* (Verbatim #Family, 3, IT), spending more time with their children (Verbatim #Family, 2, PL), learning alongside them (Verbatim #Family, 2, PL), and helping them organize their time to better complete school tasks (Verbatim #Family, 2, PL). Positive reinforcement is commonly used to build motivation and confidence (Verbatim #Family, 2, PL). These approaches reflect a deep commitment to their children's development and a belief in collaborative problem-solving between parents and children. However, families also point to systemic and institutional challenges that affect their relationship with schools and the support available for the students. A recurring concern is the lack of sufficient financial support – families highlight the need for school-based municipal aid, such as scholarships, to reduce barriers to participation. They also recommend extending school hours to better support both students' learning and family schedules (Verbatim #Family, 1, IT).

Beyond logistics, there is a strong call for *better teacher preparation and classroom conditions*. Many families feel that teachers are not adequately equipped to manage students with behavioural and learning challenges (Verbatim #Family, 3, SP). They stress the need for more specialised training and for a greater presence of support teachers, as current staffing levels often do not allow for meaningful intervention. Teachers working alone frequently struggle to continue teaching when difficulties arise.

Additionally, families underline the importance of *reducing class sizes*, as overcrowded classrooms prevent teachers from giving students the individual attention and supervision they need.

NEETs

In the **NEETs** life stories shared by young people who dropped out of school and re-engaged through second chance education, a complex picture emerges of disengagement, institutional shortcomings, and personal resilience. One of the underlying themes is the *underestimation of the role of school*, which often begins within the family context. When families themselves have had limited educational opportunities or feel little value in formal education as a path to social mobility, trust in the school system weakens. In such environments, school is not perceived as meaningful, and young people may leave the system without strong resistance or guidance. However, in many of the cases reviewed, the students themselves later developed different views from their families and chose to re-enter education through alternative routes such as second chance schools.

The *decision to leave school* is rarely attributed to a single event. Rather, it represents a turning point within a broader, often difficult, trajectory. It is almost never experienced as a free or deliberate choice, but as a consequence, frequently traumatic, arising from a convergence of factors. One significant issue raised by participants is the rigidity of the school system, which they experienced as unable or unwilling to respond to their individual needs and circumstances. The educational institution often remains narrowly focused on curricular objectives, overlooking students' emotional needs, personal contexts, and the importance of relational care. These results in environments where teaching is reduced to the delivery of content, with little space for active listening and support.

A recurring problem is the *lack of personalised guidance*. Many families, despite their intentions, lack the knowledge or tools to support their children's educational paths. This often leads to decisions that, while well-meaning, complicate rather than clarify future prospects. Simultaneously, students report that schools struggle to recognise or adapt to individual vulnerabilities (Verbatim #Male, Poland, 1), especially in cases of social and emotional difficulty. The homogeneity of expectations placed on all students clashes with the growing diversity of student backgrounds, and many feel unsupported, misunderstood, or simply invisible within the system. Terms like "unfair", "help", "understanding", and "support" frequently appear in the narratives, pointing to a strong desire for more humanised and adaptive educational environments.

For some, this *rigidity* took on harsher forms. The students recall experiences of humiliation, emotional neglect and punitive disciplinary measures – including deprivation of liberty – that left lasting negative effects. The physical spaces of schools, such as corridors and waiting areas, were also described as emotionally charged or anxiety-inducing, particularly in the context of conflict with peers or staff. In contrast, *second-chance schools* are almost unanimously seen as places of opportunity and transformation. Relationships with these institutions are described as far more positive than

those with previous schools. Students highlight the way these schools make an effort to understand each student's circumstances and approach education with greater flexibility and empathy. Teachers in these settings are perceived as supportive and respectful, fostering students' autonomy and helping them to rebuild self-esteem. Their role is understood not simply as instructors, but as allies in the students' effort to graduate, with a clearer awareness that academic success is tied to emotional well-being and personal growth. Bonding with peers in these environments also appears easier and more authentic. Shared life experiences and a clearer sense of vocational direction often create a foundation for friendship and solidarity. This sense of belonging, absent in previous institutions, plays a crucial role in sustaining students' re-engagement with education.

Looking ahead, the narratives are often framed by a discourse of *individual effort and self-improvement*. Many of the students express motivation and determination to succeed, especially those who have already experienced significant positive change in their lives. It is not surprising, given their backgrounds, that they interpret success as something earned through personal struggle, often in the absence of institutional or family support. However, it is also important to recognise that this perspective is shaped by broader societal narratives that place responsibility for both failure and success squarely on the individual.

TEACHERS

From the **teachers'** perspective, a *Safe School culture* should promote a sense of belonging to the school community, foster empathy and understanding, and welcome diversity. Teachers stress the importance of extracurricular activities that involve the whole educational community. Moreover, they add the need for commitment from the school management and for school protocols and procedures to prevent and deal with conflicts. They remark on the importance of positive relationships among teachers and the involvement of families. Likewise, there is a need for physical spaces where students feel calm, comfortable, and safe, as well as for times and spaces to be made available for teachers to work together. Finally, they highlight the need to have an adequate number of students per classroom in order to be able to meet their needs, and the need for counsellors and other specialists within and outside the school to support the work of teachers.

The teachers also remark on *the role of school management and public administration*: the management team needs to establish a clear vision of what ST means for the school and position itself as an authority figure who shares, communicates and maintains close relationships with students and other members of the educational community. They need to be active in making proposals for the prevention and resolution of problems within this community and promote extracurricular activities in which the whole educational community comes together. In relation to teaching staff, management teams need to support, listen to and consider teachers' opinions, provide them with spaces for collaborative work and reflection, and attend to their needs. Furthermore, they

remark that it is essential that the management team and administration promote the professional development of teachers in ST and provide programmes or reference guides for families to support learning at home.

Public administration can work to break down perceived barriers to ST by ensuring the stability of education laws and supporting public policies that facilitate ST. The teachers highlighted on several occasions the need for the bureaucratic workload not to be excessive so that teachers can focus on other needs, such as lesson planning, producing materials, attending to students individually, meeting with families, or working collaboratively with other teachers.

STAKEHOLDERS AND POLICYMAKERS

Across the six countries involved in the study, **stakeholders and policymakers** identified shared priorities to improve educational systems and promote teacher well-being. While national contexts vary, there is a broad agreement that *systemic changes* must centre on the emotional health of teachers, school collaboration, inclusive practices, and responsiveness to local needs.

A key area of consensus is the importance of *ongoing teacher training and professional development*. Stakeholders emphasise the need to equip educators with practical tools to navigate both their own mental health and that of their students. Essential training includes mindfulness, inclusive methodologies, mental health awareness, classroom management, and universal design for learning. This kind of preparation helps teachers navigate the complexities of today's classrooms and foster greater confidence and competence.

Equally important is the *relational dimension of school life*. Many stakeholders stress that positive relationships among teachers, staff and students are foundational to teacher well-being. Creating time and space for connection - through shared activities, regular meetings, or informal gatherings – reduces isolation and fosters mutual trust and support. Peer collaboration, collective problem-solving, and involvement in school projects enhance a sense of ownership and belonging (Verbatims #Stakeholder, 1, PT; #Stakeholder, 1, LT), while reflection and professional dialogue outside of teaching hours help sustain motivation and cohesion within teaching teams.

Stakeholders also call for more *flexibility and innovation in teaching*. Teachers should have more autonomy to adapt curricula to students' needs and personal teaching styles. Promoting creativity and shared goals enhances engagement and innovation across the school community (Verbatim #Stakeholder, 4, LT). Flexibility also means adapting to the evolving challenges of education, recognising that one-size-fits-all approaches are no longer sufficient.

Incentives and recognition are viewed as vital to maintaining motivation. Recognition can take both financial and non-financial forms – from public awards and cultural outings to tangible well-being perks like equipment and team-building experiences (Verbatim #Stakeholder, 3, PL). Acknowledging

extra effort and improving the social status of teachers, particularly in countries like Poland (Verbatim #Stakeholder, 3, PL), where it remains low, are seen as key to reversing disillusionment and burnout. Burnout itself is pointed out as a pressing concern, with many teachers overwhelmed by the emotional demands of their roles, especially in trying to meet the needs of students and families without adequate support. Addressing this requires localised, teacher-centred well-being initiatives within a flexible legal framework (Verbatim #Policymaker, 1, PL).

Stakeholders call for *reforms to reduce administrative burdens, focus on motivation, and allow schools to operate in more human-centred ways*. Parental involvement is also seen as essential for easing the emotional load on teachers and improving student outcomes. Additionally, there is a call for adopting evidence-based motivational strategies from other countries to promote innovation while respecting local contexts.

Collaboration between different educational actors is critical but underdeveloped. Stakeholders point to the need for more coordination between public and private schools, municipalities, and regional administrations. They recommend structured planning, shared successful practices and clearer guidelines to enhance joint efforts. Strengthening ties between schools and municipalities, promoting inclusive education through co-teaching and diversity professionals, and improving class organisation are priorities. Greater involvement of the educational community and decentralising some educational responsibilities to local administrations, with adequate regional support, are also proposed.

Addressing the *needs of vulnerable students* is another priority. Stakeholders emphasise tackling growing inequality, particularly among disadvantaged, rural, and minority students (e.g., Roma), through holistic education approaches, equal access to language and higher education, and the enforcement of anti-discrimination policies. Improving teacher training focused on inclusion and shifting attitudes at both institutional and individual levels is considered key.

Monitoring and evaluation are viewed as crucial tools for improvement. Regular, municipality-level evaluations are needed to identify strengths and areas of development, ultimately strengthening the education system (Verbatim #Stakeholder, 1, LT).

3.4. Cross-country conclusions and methodological reflection on co-creation and empowerment

The cross-country analysis across Spain, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Bulgaria and Lithuania reveals **consistent patterns regarding emotional needs, educational disengagement, and resilience**, despite differences in local contexts. Interviews with families, stakeholders and policymakers, life stories with NEETs and focus groups with teachers provide a comprehensive view of the challenges and potential for resilience in each context.

The families universally highlighted the importance of *emotional security, affection, and care*, particularly from parental figures, with a particular emphasis on mothers. Children's emotional discomfort was expressed through behaviours like withdrawal, crying, or seeking comfort through affectionate gestures. Self-regulation strategies, largely supported by adult figures, involved conversation, physical contact, and comforting routines such as stories or the use of comfort objects. The ability of parents to interpret non-verbal cues, particularly in neurodiverse or emotionally under-resourced environments, was also seen as vital in addressing children's needs. In more urbanised counties like Spain, Italy, and Lithuania institutional support was more readily available for addressing emotional well-being compared to more vulnerable regions like parts of Bulgaria and Poland, where systemic barriers limit such support.

The interviews with stakeholders and policymakers revealed both shared priorities and contextual differences across countries. There is broad agreement on the importance of family-school collaboration, emotional stability at home, and increased human resources to support inclusive education. While Portugal, Spain, and Italy demonstrate progress in structured inclusion models, countries like Bulgaria and Poland face persistent challenges related to structural barriers, teacher status, and rural equity. Despite these differences, stakeholders stress the importance of local adaptability, active listening, and community engagement to foster emotionally safe and inclusive schools. Additionally, in both the FG and the observations, there was alignment in the elements and actions that were considered relevant to ST. Teachers confirmed several elements that strengthen or weaken teaching practice in regard to ST, stressing the central role of teachers and the relationships they establish with their students. They highlighted the influence that the different agents involved in education have on ST and the need for all of them to collaborate. Here we are referring to families, teaching faculty, other educational specialists, management teams and public administration, all of whom can contribute through their roles to ST.

In terms of educational disengagement, the Photovoice technique revealed shared experiences across countries. Family instability, lack of teacher understanding, bullying, and poverty emerging as key contributing factors to NEETs disengagement. Many participants described feeling excluded due to rigid school systems and a lack of supportive environments. However, second-chance schools were widely seen as crucial spaces for re-engagement, offering empathy, respect and opportunities to rebuild relationships. These schools played a key role in fostering resilience, proving a space for NEETs to reconnect with education and develop new life trajectories. Yet, the severity of vulnerability varied across countries. In Bulgaria and Poland, participants often reported more extreme circumstances such as family violence, homelessness, and abandonment without any support networks, leading to heightened disengagement. In contrast, NEETs from Portugal, Italy and Spain, while facing hardships, more frequently encountered early reconnection with education systems, which help them re-engage more effectively. Cultural differences also influenced perceptions, with Lithuania and Poland

recognising education as a means of social exclusion, while NEETs from Italy and Bulgaria expressed greater disillusionment with the traditional education system. Despite these differences, access to supportive educational contexts and the resilience of individual participants were key factors in overcoming barriers and reconstructing life trajectories.

The methodological aspect of this research emphasises **participatory approaches** such as Photovoice and collaborative research with teachers, which played a crucial role in fostering self-reflection and co-creating the theoretical model of the project.

For many NEETs participants, the Photovoice activity became a powerful tool for self-reflection, enabling them to revisit their past. In some cases, particularly when their current situation was stable, participants engaged deeply with the exercise, reflecting on their histories with a sense of pride or romanticism. The exercise "What would you say to someone who is in the situation you have been in" proved to be particularly emotional, as it encouraged participants to empathise with their younger selves, often confronting feelings of guilt while recognizing their personal growth. This process allowed many NEETs to access and articulate feelings they had never shared before, revealing the power of the exercise to activate empathy and self-pity, thereby fostering emotional healing.

In parallel, action research has been carried out through a collaborative working method with teachers from different educational stages. This allowed teachers to take on a research role as they collected data and reflected on their experiences in the classroom. In this way, co-creation has been the relationship between the teachers and the other research actors, which means that it has been horizontal, collaborative and mutually enriching. Teachers are valued in this project as the experts in the teaching-learning relationship and those who can offer essential knowledge about teaching at the school level.

Regarding the research process carried out, we would highlight that the FG acted as a starting point to get to know the teachers' voices and their perceptions and reflections regarding ST. Their suggestions on how it can be applied in classrooms and schools gave rise to two observation tools. Subsequently, the observation process served to strengthen and complement the reflections previously given by the teachers with evidence from the classroom. It gathered enriching information on how the teacher's bond with their students manifests in the participating teachers' classrooms, how they approach ST in their day-to-day practice and how their schools work towards ST. Additionally, the observation process validated the usefulness of the observation tools in varied school contexts and improved them through the integration of the teachers' feedback.

It is worth noting that the teachers highly valued the observation process. In addition to identifying aspects related to the ST, they were able to get to know themselves better as teachers, identify their strengths and areas for improvement, address insecurities derived from being observed by another teacher, learn from their colleagues and reflect collaboratively with other teachers. The insights

provided in this collaborative research with teachers allow triangulation of the ST theoretical framework and show the ST model's validity in real European contexts of application. The materials produced, particularly the Safe Teaching Observation tool, the Pedagogical Reflection tool and the Teacher's Workbooks in which teachers share their reflections, are intended to be disseminated to the wider educational community as part of the ST toolkit. The aim is that they will guide other teachers, management teams and decision makers in introducing ST as a priority and developing it in their respective contexts.

4. General conclusions

This report presents a comprehensive methodological outline and analysis of the empirical findings derived from various qualitative data collections of the LET'S CARE project. The findings underscore the significance of fostering a secure environment where educators feel supported and valued, thereby creating a conducive atmosphere for learning. This necessitates motivated, well-compensated teachers who are adept at adapting teaching methods to accommodate students' diverse needs, thereby cultivating a relationship based on mutual trust and esteem. Furthermore, it is imperative to reform the system, including hiring dedicated educators, involving parents, and updating educational standards to meet the needs of today's youth. Additionally, it is important to invest in education, nurture soft skills, and prioritise individualised approaches over administrative measures. The analysis of participant perspectives advocates for the cohesive implementation of reforms, efficient resource allocation, and augmented school budgets to facilitate extracurricular activities and broaden students' experiential learning opportunities. Moreover, collaborative efforts across administrative bodies and sectors, underlining the significance of inclusive education, co-teaching, and the active involvement of the entire educational community, have been pointed out. As a result, all these findings have contributed to comprehensively defining the Safe Education Theoretical Model.

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Annex I: Tables of profiles and quotes from families, stakeholders, policymakers, NEETs and teachers

Table 1. Profiles of interviewed families

COUNTRY OF THE INTERVIEW	FAMILY ID NUMBER	PARENTS' PROFILE	CHILDREN'S PROFILE
BULGARIA	BG/FAM1	Roma family Mother is 14 years old, and Father – 16 years old	3 children: 11, 9 and 5 years old. The older children go to school and the little ones go to kindergarten.
BULGARIA	BG/FAM2	Roma family	4 children: 1 - a boy who has successfully completed 4th grade / initial stage / and continues his education in a sports school; 3 girls: 15 years old - he studies in a vocational high school, at 2 years and 6 months, and the youngest is 5 months old.
BULGARIA	BG/FAM3	Parents have different religious backgrounds. They were brought up in two different ethnicities – Turkish (minority) and Bulgarian.	3 children: The eldest child is 9 years old, a girl, a schoolgirl; A 7-year-old boy. And a 2-year-old girl.
BULGARIA	BG/FAM4	Roma Family	3 children: a 9-year-old girl, an 11-year-old boy. and a boy of 14 years. Children attend school regularly, speak foreign languages
ITALY	IT/FAM1	Extended family (mum, dad, 2 daughters and an uncle)	2 children: 7 and 10 years old
ITALY	IT/FAM2	Rural Setting	2 children: 7 and 10 years old.
ITALY	IT/FAM3	Average socio-economic status	3 children: 6, 10, 15 years old.
ITALY	IT/FAM4	Rural Setting	4 children: 1, 7, 9, 11 years old.

LITHUANIA	LT/FAM1	Emigrant background	4 children: 10 (with autism); 12; 6, 3 years old.
LITHUANIA	LT/FAM2	Family divorced	2 children: 22 and 12 years old.
LITHUANIA	LT/FAM3	Emigrant background	2 children: 12 (with hyperactivity and attention disorders) and 6 years old.
LITHUANIA	LT/FAM4	Single-parent family (mother)	Two children from different families (divorced parents) with 12 years difference between them: 21 and 9 years old.
POLAND	PL/FAM1	Mother aged 45, a father aged 52 living in suburban areas near Krakow.	3 children: a daughter aged 16 and a son aged 12, a daughter in the first grade of high school, a son in the 6th grade of primary school.
POLAND	PL/FAM2	Rural Setting	Two children. Daughter (12 years old) goes to 6th grade of primary school from September. Son (6 years old) is in kindergarten, going to school next year.
POLAND	PL/FAM3	Emigrant background	Two boys. One is 4 years old and the other is 3 years old and both go to a public kindergarten
POLAND	PL/FAM4	The parents are on attendance benefits because the children absorb a huge amount of time and care	Two twin boys, who are 13 years old. The boys have autism, one of them also has epilepsy and both have moderate mental disabilities.
PORTUGAL	PT/FAM1	Restructured family. The mother had three children from a previous relationship in which she suffered physical and psychological abuse.	Three children (ages 3, 19, and 15)
PORTUGAL	PT/FAM2	Single-parent family, (mother). Children born from a previous relationship with physical violence	Two children – 9 and 8 years old

PORTUGAL	PT/FAM3	Mother and father	3 children (3,17,20), a girl in foster care in Guinea Bissau who was finally adopted
SPAIN	SP/FAM1	Two mothers (separated) and with an immigrant background	Two daughters aged 10 and 12
SPAIN	SP/FAM2	Rural Setting	Two daughters aged 16 and 18
SPAIN	SP/FAM3	Single-parent family (mother)	One daughter 6 years old
SPAIN	SP/FAM4	Unstructured family, with a divorced mother and father	One daughter 10 years old, with down syndrome

Table 2. Profiles of interviewed stakeholders–policymakers

COUNTRY OF THE INTERVIEW	INTERVIEW ID NUMBER	PROFILE	ROLE
BULGARIA	BG/1	Responsible for 5 urban schools and 7 rural schools and 17 kindergartens.	Policy Maker
BULGARIA	BG/2	Educator – teacher-principal. has 40 years of pedagogical experience, having held different positions in the hierarchy of the educational system.	Stakeholder
BULGARIA	BG/3	15 years of management experience all in difficult schools. Engineer by profession.	Stakeholder
BULGARIA	BG/4	Direct connection with education. Relationship with children and families at risk. Under the guidance are the Social Centres for Accommodation of Children with and without Damage, a Community Support Center for Prevention of Abandonment of Children and Consultations for Dropping Out of School, Social Integration of Children from Institutions.	Policy Maker
ITALY	IT/1	Headmaster of an Institute. Educator	Stakeholder

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		in an educational community for minors taken away from their families by the court.	
ITALY	IT/2	Headmaster and Director of Education. Graduated in Pedagogy. Writer for pedagogical journals and books.	Policy Maker
ITALY	IT/3	Educator and teacher. Headmaster of an Istituto. Three university degrees: literature, philosophy, pedagogical sciences with a focus on adult education.	Stakeholder
ITALY	IT/4	Director at the Ambito Territoriale	Policy Maker
ITALY	IT/5	Inspector General of the Regional Education Office. Headmistress on territorial school office.	Policy Maker
LITHUANIA	LT/1	Director of School. 25 years of teaching experience.	Stakeholder
LITHUANIA	LT/2	More than 20 years of experience as a preschool teacher. Currently at the education department of a District Municipality.	Policy Maker
LITHUANIA	LT/3	For the past five years, he has spearheaded the NGO, overseeing its commitment to delivering impactful educational and cultural services.	Stakeholder
LITHUANIA	LT/4	Adviser at Ministry Level. Areas of responsibility: inclusive education, civic education, etc.	Policy Maker
POLAND	PL/1	Councillor of a commune. Teacher in the high school.	Policy Maker
POLAND	PL/2	Active politician for many years in education area.	Policy Maker

POLAND	PL/3	Teacher of early childhood education and pre-school education. Work in the fields of surdopedagogy, tyflopädagogik, oligophrenopedagogik and working with children on the autism spectrum.	Stakeholder
POLAND	PL/4	Teacher psychologist for 16 years in a psychological counselling centre. Ex deputy director.	Stakeholder
PORTUGAL	PT/1	Bachelor's degree in education. Teacher with more than 20 years of experience in a school in the North of Portugal.	Stakeholder
PORTUGAL	PT/2	Master's in psychology of education and school psychology. Different civic-politic roles (a school psychologist as a research, as a local councillor, in the educational area).	Policy Maker
PORTUGAL	PT/3	Headmaster, with training as elementary school teacher, with a specialization in special education and with a Master's degree in School Administration.	Stakeholder
PORTUGAL	PT/4	Director from the Ministry of Education. Consultant and teacher in higher education.	Policy Maker
SPAIN	SP/1	Community Services Teacher. Director of a Guidance Team in which there are professionals from which there are professionals of Educational Guidance and Community Services and which and primary schools in a specific sector.	Stakeholder
SPAIN (SP)	SP/2	Head of Academic Coordination in Extremadura.	Policy Maker

SPAIN	SP/3	Teacher of Therapeutic Pedagogy and Hearing and Language. Technical Teaching Advisor in the Regional Ministry of Extremadura.	Stakeholder
SPAIN	SP/4	Head of Public Entity. Physical Education Teacher.	Policy Maker

Table 3. Profiles of interviewed NEETs

COUNTRY	SUBJECT OF STUDY	GENDER	AGE	BRIEF DESCRIPTION
BULGARIA	SUBJECT 1	male	17	Feels safe in the classroom, but not in common areas where peers show aggressive behaviour. Past with integration difficulties due to dialect, loneliness problems and bad company. Parents not always supportive (one died, the other alcoholism), likes quiet and solitary activities. In process of reconciliation with school.
BULGARIA	SUBJECT 2	female	18	She was wary of this procedure, in the end she agreed. Very difficult childhood, violence at home and neglectful parents. She dropped out of school, led to living on the street. Bad company, theft and risky behaviour. She left her mother's house, looked for her father, he ignored her. In constant search and resilience. Very connected to her emotions. Now she has a job and is confident in herself and her future.
ITALY	SUBJECT 1	female	20	Migrated from Romania. Family as good main support, concerned about her future (except her father). Bad experience at school, with teachers and classmates, in first school in Italy, in first community. Currently in another school has good relationship with both and very good school performance.
ITALY	SUBJECT 2	female	19	She dropped out of school, as did her two older brothers, because of poor results, she did not feel supported. Humiliation by teachers, very

				severe punishments. The family has been supportive, although they seem to be very demanding of her.
ITALY	SUBJECT 3	female	21	Bullying by classmates. Defiant and rebellious attitude towards teachers. Harmful parent, with whom he has no current contact. The girl took up her studies again mainly because of her parents' insistence. Her voice was not heard, she needed time to choose her path. Currently, good results in second chance school.
LITHUANIA	SUBJECT 1	male	39	Left school to go to a vocational school, but did not finish it either due to a bad social situation. The second time the relationship with teachers was better. At the moment he has not finished his studies, but he has a job, a house, a family and wishes to improve in the future.
LITHUANIA	SUBJECT 2	female	44	He was doing well in his studies, but his living conditions were such that he had to leave school to work. She is currently angry about the fact that she had to drop out, she felt abandoned by her parents when she had to make this decision. She continues to study while working and has a family of her own.
POLAND	SUBJECT 1	male	25	Very harsh memories of the past, with bad company which he considers to be the cause of his dropping out of school (several drop-outs). His parents have alcoholism problems, there is violence in the home and they do not attend to him, he is left in the care of his grandmother, and when she dies he becomes depressed. Very aware of his process, he has gone to therapy and it has been a trigger for change and overcoming his problems. He has a job as a cook, although he still depends on social benefits.
POLAND	SUBJECT 2	female	25	Her father abandoned them during her childhood. She was a good student, but had a child at an early age, which caused her to drop out of school. She later broke up with that

				partner due to alcoholism problems. She faces her future with determination and the strength to know what she does not want in her life.
PORTUGAL	SUBJECT 1	male	18	He migrated to Spain for a while. Left school due to illness (physical and anxiety) and experienced it as an unfair fact, his parents did not support him. Now good relationship with the educational institution , problems with anxiety and phobias, in current treatment and good prognosis. Dreams of progress in life and work.
PORTUGAL	SUBJECT 2	male	21	Good student, but dropped out of school due to constant change of city (migration to France) and bad economic situation. Homeless for a while. Ran away from home due to bad family relationship, stole in the street. No family support in second chance school. Rejection of delinquent behaviour, improved relationship with teachers.
SPAIN	SUBJECT 1	male	14	Social avoidance, his unsafe place is the classroom. Prefers to stay in places without people, alone (or with animals). Missing school due to lack of parental care.
SPAIN	SUBJECT 2	female	14	He has lost interest in seeking positive reinforcement from teachers. Hates two of his teachers. Punishment as a useless mechanism. She is completely disconnected from academics, but shows interest in emotional issues and sports.

Table 4. Examples of verbatim quotes from families interviewed

ID	VERBATIMS
Family,2, SP	<i>"I have always met professionally qualified people who interact with students as growing individuals with needs and not just as people who have to learn concepts or knowledge." It provides a "safe physical and emotional environment, clear rules, agreements and commitment to follow by the entire school community".</i>
Family, 3, IT	<i>"For example, our son was afraid to speak in front of the class, so we came up with the idea of recording presentations, and when he had the courage to speak in front of the class, he started giving presentations in class. These strategies are very helpful."</i>

<p>Family,4, BG</p>	<p><i>‘Children at school should not only accumulate knowledge and develop intellectually, they should learn how to treat others, accept differences, be tolerant and ultimately become adults who will one day live in a society with rules and customs.’</i></p> <p><i>"It is difficult for a parent to understand what positive actions a teacher takes in case of conflict: the parent is not in the classroom, the teacher does not always explain what happened and how he/she acted for now the children do not always tell and when they do, they obviously express their point of view which is very subjective, especially in an elementary school." "(...) when he started saying he didn't want to go, I don't know what, and I thought something was wrong because he is a child who talks about school even during vacations and sometimes I say I'm tired of hearing about school (...) when a child no longer has that enthusiasm for school, something is going on, you have to look into it right away."</i></p>
<p>Family,2, BG</p>	<p><i>" If there are problems with other children, the school refers them to the police. It is a very difficult class where it is impossible to communicate with the children's parents. There is nothing the school can do."</i></p> <p><i>" They don't invite us to anything because the school doesn't want to have problems, because when we say something, it's immediately that we have complaints about everything and the child has a problem."</i></p>
<p>Family, 4, IT</p>	<p><i>‘Few children are always enthusiastic about going to school; they go because they have to. I think that if the school environment were more “comfortable” and offered alternative activities, there would be more enthusiasm.’ My daughter is not very talkative, so I don't always know what happens in class, but one thing is certain: she really admires her teachers for their patience and determination."</i></p>
<p>Family, 3, IT</p>	<p><i>‘My son sometimes tells me that the teacher, to calm down a classmate with a disability, stops lecturing and focuses on him. That's fine. But if there was a support teacher present, she could consider taking him out of class for a few minutes to calm him down and restore calm. Support hours are becoming fewer and fewer, and unfortunately, the children who need them are becoming more and more numerous.’</i></p>
<p>Family,4, IT</p>	<p><i>‘Trust in schools needs to be improved. Schools should be open and provide spaces for dialogue with the local community, even outside school hours. The administration should facilitate these activities. For example, by creating cultural exchange days and opportunities to meet the various ethnic groups in the area.’</i></p>
<p>Family,3, LT</p>	<p><i>‘Parents of weaker children are not as active as parents of stronger children, so the minority has no influence on the decisions made.’ (...) "then, from this point of view, a bad emotional state definitely translates into bad academic performance" (...) since "a cold school environment that does not take into account your child's needs leave your child out. If you're an awkward child, there will be problems. Teachers want to work with strong children."</i></p>
<p>Family,2,LT</p>	<p><i>“There is no good coordination in the school or between teachers and families. Additionally, there is a lot of teacher turnover, which does not favour this coordination. "If I had to answer the question of how our kindergarten teachers meet the emotional needs of the children, I don't know what to say. And I don't know if they know them at all. Sometimes I get the feeling that it's simply the case that the teachers are just tasked with taking care of the children and feeding them and are not interested in their emotional needs and expect the children to take them home."</i></p>

<p>Family, 4, LT</p>	<p><i>‘For the school to be open and not deny problems, but start solving them. If you go alone, with no one paying attention, it becomes your problem alone.’ ‘I want my daughter to feel good, and when she feels good, to achieve what she wants in life.’ “I hope the situation changes for the better. There is a great need for teachers with a different approach in schools. Less control, less pressure, more optimism. To encourage a child, a teacher must motivate them positively and not diminish their self-esteem. <... > Today we need critical and creative thinkers, and school does not prepare them. School prepares ordinary factory workers. School should help, discover and strengthen a child's strengths. Now we still have to work on the education system. The government is passing a law, but teachers and schools have neither the means nor the opportunity to implement it.’ “If teachers would take action it would help to restore balance in student-teacher relationships”.</i></p>
<p>Family, 1, PL</p>	<p><i>‘When difficulties arise, children drop out of school and deny these problems. They simply close the case. The problem resurfaces the next day because they have to go back to school and there may be problems.’</i></p>
<p>Family, 4, PL</p>	<p><i>‘Children do not seek help from teachers because it was useless, so they gave up. They do not even want help; no one helps them, neither psychologists nor educators.’ “We value our relationship with the school very poorly. The teachers don't want to help, we have asked for help many times and it always came back to us. It was the same with my parents. The teachers pretend there is no problem, they keep most of it”.</i></p>
<p>Family, 3, PL</p>	<p><i>‘It's hard to say what children like and dislike about interacting with other children because I think they enjoy it in general, even if someone is cruel to them because children sometimes don't understand other people's intentions. Any attention is good for them and the fact that someone has taken an interest in them.’</i></p>
<p>Family, 1, PL</p>	<p><i>‘Like any mother, I would like my son to have the best education possible, but at this point it's fair to say that I would like them to finish school at the last possible moment. I would like them to be educated in such a way that it is easy for them to find a job and do what they like and what they are good at.’</i></p>
<p>Family, 1, PL</p>	<p><i>‘We rate our relationship with the school very poorly. The teachers don't want to help; we've asked for help many times and it always backfired on us. It was the same with my parents. The teachers pretend there's no problem; they side with the majority.’</i></p>
<p>Family, 4, IT</p>	<p><i>"A safe environment materialises when a teacher feels safe, that is when he/she feels understood and supported by his/her colleagues and the school principal. There should always be highly motivated teachers, this would naturally result in a safe environment. Teachers should always support students and not burden them with mistakes but help them understand that [they] can be a starting point for success; they should always be by their side, supporting them, encouraging them. A safe school is a healthy environment where teachers can do their job and where students feel understood and supported. To be motivating, a teacher must be ready to change their teaching methods if he sees that the one in place is not working, find alternative methods to capture students' attention. The school's main task is to create a safe environment where children and teachers can live together in a peaceful atmosphere. The principal must take steps to create this environment where conflicts, which [are] normal ..., can also be managed to be easily resolved. A secure teacher-student relationship exists if there is mutual trust and esteem. The attitude of teachers towards children is fundamental. They must stimulate ... curiosity for the children. When children feel listened to, they in turn are more attentive during the lesson. The teacher must be able to make the children feel worthy and capable."</i></p>

	<i>"The safe school is one that communicates serenity and acceptance, which puts the emotional-relational aspect ahead of [academics]"</i> .
Family, 2, SP	<i>"These goals (well-being at school) can only be achieved if education systems are truly equitable and inclusive. They must ensure that all learners have a chance to fulfil their potential, irrespective of personal circumstances, family, cultural and socio-economic backgrounds. However, today not all young people in Europe have equal opportunities to benefit from education."</i>
Family,3, SP	<i>"For example, foreign families who do not know the language hardly participate when apps could be developed that translate easily and so the school could open up to these people or incorporate intercultural mediators". "To reduce disparities and promote inclusion, it is necessary for the school to propose activities outside the school curriculum that are highly inclusive, such as sports activities, because being playful activities they are likely to engage all children much more easily, also on an emotional level." "It is important to build strong partnerships with third sector organizations that provide educational and social assistance and support." "Trust in schools needs to be improved. Schools must be open and provide spaces for dialogue with the local community, even outside school hours. The administration should facilitate these activities. For example, by creating cultural exchange days and opportunities to meet the various ethnic groups in the area."</i>
Family,2, PL	<i>"Always with as calm a tone and conversation as possible" (...) To motivate them and incorporate learning at home". (...) "Teaching them not to leave everything to the last minute" (...)."For example, he knows he can go with us to the superhero park when they finish their homework".</i>
Family, 1, IT	<i>"Families go through a small crisis when the school is closed. They chose the full-time school because then they are guaranteed an environment where there are people to take care of the growth of our children until the afternoon. Beyond the school, they need to provide families with a service that, through playful activities, can welcome the children and take care of them. Not everyone has caregivers or grandparents"</i> .
Family, 3, IT	<i>"As a middle-level school, it is hard to realise much. I would like to see more extracurricular activities, more interesting activities/lessons for elementary students and extended schooling for all elementary students, not just first graders. More play spaces because the school is very empty. More activities for the older classes. I would like more information, evaluation of the school's work and achievements. More meetings for parents, more internal support"</i> .
Family, 4, PT	<i>"The first thing is for the children to share it with the teachers. Then the teachers talk to the children, without shouting, and quickly inform the families about the situations created. Then the parents intervene, with quick and direct information from the school. In addition, sometimes, a person from the school (security guards or mediators) talks to the families. This person is from the neighbourhood and is of Roma ethnicity"</i> .

Table 5. Examples of verbatim quotes from NEETs Photovoice

ID	VERBATIMS
Female Italy 3	<i>"There was a moment in my life [when she left school] when I was about to lose myself, my confidence, all my passions and everything. It was a bit of a dark moment because I didn't think I could go on"</i> .
Female, Lithuania 2	<i>"You don't want to descend into that asocial life"</i>

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Male, Portugal 2	<i>“My father called me a donkey because I was going back to school and wasting my time again”.</i>
Female, Poland, 2	<i>“[My mother] just made sure to inform the school of the problems the family had, including financial ones, thanks to which she could be exempted from certain fees, for example for school meals or school trips”.</i>
Male, Poland 1	<i>“I had to overcome the fear of accepting help from another person, a mega challenge for me. Then to trust the other person. A person as wounded as me, with such disturbed relationships, cannot trust, is afraid of being hurt”.</i>

Table 6. Examples of verbatim quotes from policy makers and stakeholders interviewed

ID	VERBATIMS
Polycymaker, 2 PL	<i>“We understand the term student-friendly school a little differently. In our general understanding, this means that there are desks, it is clean, there is equipment to facilitate education, but that is not what friendliness is about. School is still missing an element that encourages children to go to school, to go with interest in what might happen today, it won't be a boring lesson where I won't have to learn from one page to another by heart, where you will use half of the break to give me an assignment because she didn't have time to do it during class. Let me give you one example: my friend's son went to a mechatronics technical school. After graduating, he didn't really know what to do next, whether to study this field or go into something else. But he decided to try and went to study in London. After 3 months, he called his mother to say that he already knew what he wanted to do in life. His mother asked him how he knew this and he told her how he had to do a project and to defend this ordinary, mid-year project, professors and students came and asked him questions and he had to defend it. And it was something amazing. And if such conditions were created, especially for difficult children, because most often difficult children require special attention. And very often we marginalize them in order to move the problem away, and by marginalizing them we cause even bigger problems because the child does not see any interest in them. And if we were to teach children through such design, and this young person had to create such a project, and this project would have to be defended, and the principal, a teacher from another class, or an educator would come to defend this project, then this young person would be perceived completely differently. If we do not perceive and treat young people as partners, we will never really include them in our lives, we will never create conditions for them to feel needed, and yet every person has the need to feel needed”.</i>
Stakeholder, 1, LT	<i>“The vision of a safe school is intricately tied to the concept of a secure teacher. The teacher's role is pivotal, not only in providing physical safety but also in contributing to the overall well-being of the school community. The question of the teacher's prestige is paramount; when teachers are empowered, the school becomes a safer and more enriching environment for everyone involved”.</i>
Stakeholder, 4, LT	<i>“Nurturing a positive attitude towards children is paramount—an endeavor that involves recognizing them as individuals, each possessing unique functions and capabilities. It is crucial for teachers to establish individualized relationships with each student. This connection acts as a catalyst, not only boosting the child's motivation but also enhancing their sense of responsibility.</i>

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	<i>At the heart of this dynamic lies a foundation of respect and positivity, where the teacher serves as a pivotal role model”.</i>
Stakeholder, 3, LT	<i>“It's important to acknowledge that financial security is a valid concern, and seeking improvement in this regard is understandable. However, it's crucial to align these efforts with the genuine needs of the educational community and prioritize sustainability for long-term success”.</i>
Stakeholder,1, PT	<i>“To have confidence in your colleagues, to ask for help from everyone, and to be able to talk about your difficulties and challenges”.</i>
Policymaker, 1, PL	<i>“A motivated teacher means a motivated child. Currently, teachers' well-being is not guaranteed. Even if they had the conditions to do so, they still do not have the time because the educational system for children does not allow it. In my opinion, there are a lot of tools around, but the way the school is organized makes it impossible to use them. Therefore, an evolution of the school is needed and through evolution a revolution should take place. Despite the availability of teacher training centers, the school has not changed at all. The attitude of teachers is also a problem. Let me give you a short example of a conference for teachers, where the organizer planned the most valuable lectures at the end of the conference so that the teachers stayed until the end of the conference, but after the first break half of them left the conference. Therefore, it is also necessary to change the approach of teachers themselves”.</i>
Policymaker, 1, PL	<i>“To achieve the vision of an ideal school future, systemic reform is necessary. Conditions must be created for teachers to be motivated, professionals and enthusiasts of education. They must also be well-paid, of course. The problem is the decline of teacher authority. Parental cooperation is necessary and necessary. Educational requirements should also be adapted to contemporary youth, to their capabilities and new intellectual predispositions and knowledge acquisition. Young people need other means to reach them. It is necessary to develop soft skills, various design methods, etc. It is also necessary to constantly equalize the opportunities of rural areas with urban areas and access to higher culture”.</i>
Stakeholder, 3, PL	<i>“All these things give our staff the opportunity to relax, breathe and fill up with energy for the working days ahead of them”.</i>

Table 7. Number of teachers in each Focus Group by country

COUNTRY	NUMBER OF PARTICIPATING TEACHERS FG1	NUMBER OF PARTICIPATING TEACHERS FG2	NUMBER OF PARTICIPATING TEACHERS FG3
Bulgaria	5	8	5
Italy	10	5	N/A
Lithuania	4	6	N/A
Poland	7	8	N/A
Portugal	7	6	N/A
Spain	10	9	N/A

Total per Focus Group	43	42	5
Total	90		

Table 8. Number of teachers who participated in teaching observations by school and country

COUNTRY	NUMBER OF TEACHERS SCHOOL ONE	NUMBER OF TEACHERS SCHOOL TWO	NUMBER OF TEACHERS SCHOOL THREE	TOTAL PER COUNTRY
Bulgaria	4	3	4	11
Italy	6	6	X	12
Lithuania	N/A	N/A	X	10
Poland	7	7	X	14
Portugal	2	1	X	3
Spain	6	6	X	12
Total	62			

Table 9. Number of teachers by age

AGE	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
Between 20 and 30	7
Between 30 and 40	12
Between 40 and 50	37
Between 50 and 60	26
Between 60 and 70	8

Table 10. Number of teachers by gender

GENDER	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
Female	73
Male	16
Does not indicate	1

Table 11. Number of teachers by education level where they are teaching

EDUCATION LEVEL	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
Pre-school	6
Primary	54
Secondary	35
Special education	1

Note: 4 teachers have selected more than one stage (3 teachers ticked 2 stages and 1 ticked 3).

Table 12. Number of teachers by years of experience

YEARS AS TEACHER	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
From 0 to 10 years	21
From 10 to 20 years	16
From 20 to 30 years	34
From 30 to 40 years	15
From 40 to 50 years	4

Table 413. Profiles of teachers from Bulgaria

FOCUS GROUP 1 → 5 PARTICIPANTS				
	Age	Gender	Educational level of teaching	Years as a teacher
Participant 1	28	Female	Secondary	1
Participant 2	40	Female	Secondary	1
Participant 3	28	Female	Primary	5
Participant 4	41	Female	Secondary	11
Participant 5	36	Female	Primary	6
FOCUS GROUP 2 → 8 PARTICIPANTS				

Participant 1	60	Female	Primary	33
Participant 2	49	Female	Primary	25
Participant 3	49	Female	Primary	4
Participant 4	31	Female	Pre-school/Primary	5
Participant 5	35	Female	Primary	7 months
Participant 6	59	Female	Primary	34
Participant 7	58	Female	Primary	26
Participant 8	58	Male	Primary	29
FOCUS GROUP 3 → 5 PARTICIPANTS				
Participant 1	47	Female	Pre-school	18
Participant 2	43	Female	Pre-school/Primary	20
Participant 3	60	Female	Secondary	40
Participant 4	29	Male	Secondary	2
Participant 5	40	Female	Primary	12

Table 14. Profiles of teachers from Italy

FOCUS GROUP 1 → 10 PARTICIPANTS				
	Age	Gender	Educational level of teaching	Years as a teacher
Participant 1	54	Female	Primary	30
Participant 2	27	Female	Primary	2
Participant 3	26	Female	Primary	3

Participant 4	44	Female	Primary	20
Participant 5	43	Female	Primary	16
Participant 6	41	Female	Primary	15
Participant 7	54	Female	Primary	17
Participant 8	47	Female	Primary	17
Participant 9	44	Male	Primary	23
Participant 10	39	Female	Primary	5
FOCUS GROUP 2 → 5 PARTICIPANTS				
Participant 1	28	Male	Primary	3
Participant 2	48	Female	Primary	22
Participant 3	55	Female	Primary	36
Participant 4	52	Female	Pre-school	32
Participant 5	47	Female	Primary	28

Table 15. Profiles of teachers from Lithuania

FOCUS GROUP 1 → 4 PARTICIPANTS				
	Age	Gender	Educational level of teaching	Years as a teacher
Participant 1	50	Female	Primary/Secondary	30
Participant 2	50	Female	Primary	28
Participant 3	62	Female	Primary	42
Participant 4	47	Female	Secondary	22
FOCUS GROUP 2 → 6 PARTICIPANTS				
Participant 1	50	Female	Pre-school/Primary/Secondary	27
Participant 2	60	Male	Secondary	38
Participant 3	64	Female	Primary/Secondary	7

Participant 4	57	Female	Secondary	35
Participant 5	63	Female	Secondary	40
Participant 6	54	Female	Primary	32

Table 16. Profiles of teachers from Poland

FOCUS GROUP 1 → 7 PARTICIPANTS				
	Age	Gender	Educational level of teaching	Years as a teacher
Participant 1	33	Male	Secondary	7
Participant 2	34	Female	Secondary	7
Participant 3	37	Female	Secondary	8
Participant 4	37	Female	Secondary	12
Participant 5	39	Female	Secondary	15
Participant 6	42	Female	Secondary	18
Participant 7	54	Female	Secondary	29
FOCUS GROUP 2 → 8 PARTICIPANTS				
Participant 1	25	Male	Primary	9 months
Participant 2	32	Male	Primary	9
Participant 3	33	Female	Primary	10
Participant 4	35	Female	Primary	10
Participant 5	45	Female	Primary	16
Participant 6	48	Female	Primary	24
Participant 7	49	Female	Primary	24
Participant 8	53	Female	Primary	25

Table 17: Profiles of teachers from Portugal

FOCUS GROUP 1 → 7 PARTICIPANTS

	Age	Gender	Educational level of teaching	Years as a teacher
Participant 1	45	Female	Primary	23
Participant 2	56	Female	Secondary	33
Participant 3	55	Female	Secondary	30
Participant 4	60	Female	Pre-school	40
Participant 5	61	Female	Primary	33
Participant 6	52	N/A	Secondary	30
Participant 7	44	Female	Special education	22
FOCUS GROUP 2 → 6 PARTICIPANTS				
Participant 1	46	Male	Secondary	24
Participant 2	45	Female	Primary	22
Participant 3	43	Male	Primary	21
Participant 4	53	Male	Secondary	26
Participant 5	45	Female	Secondary	20
Participant 6	57	Female	Secondary	36

Table 18. Profiles of teachers from Spain

FOCUS GROUP 1 → 10 PARTICIPANTS				
	Age	Gender	Educational level of teaching	Years as a teacher
Participant 1	47	Male	Primary	23
Participant 2	43	Female	Primary	20
Participant 3	43	Female	Primary	20
Participant 4	49	Female	Primary	26
Participant 5	48	Female	Primary	20
Participant 6	44	Female	Primary	14
Participant 7	51	Female	Primary	28

Participant 8	46	Female	Primary	20
Participant 9	50	Female	Primary	25
Participant 10	44	Female	Primary	20
FOCUS GROUP 2 → 9 PARTICIPANTS				
Participant 1	52	Male	Secondary	24
Participant 2	57	Male	Secondary	30
Participant 3	52	Male	Secondary	6
Participant 4	41	Female	Secondary	7
Participant 5	48	Female	Secondary	21
Participant 6	51	Male	Secondary	9
Participant 7	59	Female	Secondary	27
Participant 8	46	Female	Secondary	16
Participant 9	47	Female	Secondary	15

Table 19. Examples of quotes from teachers participating in the Focus Groups and observations

ID	VERBATIMS
Teacher from Poland	<i>"When we manage to build positive relationships with parents and they understand that we want the best for their child, this is the key to creating safe teaching".</i>
Teacher from Lithuania	<i>"[It is positive that] there is a strong involvement of families in the learning process. [Yet] sometimes teachers need to limit the families' involvement, because some parents try to teach teachers how to work."</i>
Teacher from Bulgaria	<i>"It is necessary for the management team to offer programs and recommendations to guide families in the education and development of their children".</i>
Teacher from Bulgaria	<i>"[Teachers] hold personal meetings with parents, at which they first emphasize children's achievements and carefully talk about the needs of the student."</i>
Teacher from Spain	<i>"A teacher who asks how their students feel, who connects with them and actively listens to them, is able to capture their attention and achieve better results both emotionally and academically".</i>
Teacher from Lithuania	<i>"The teacher consistently demonstrates tact and ethical behaviour towards the pupils, maintaining a respectful demeanour throughout."</i>

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Teacher from Bulgaria	<i>"The teacher should be able to help his students identify and express their emotions. [...] The teacher needs to develop cooperation between students who come from different backgrounds and have different needs and interests".</i>
Teacher from Spain	<i>"Sometimes you have to forget the curricular part and focus on working on emotional aspects and personal values".</i>
Teacher from Poland	<i>"[Safe Teaching] is acceptance, understanding and an individual approach - not throwing everyone into one bag, because everyone comes to school with a different story, different baggage of experience and has different needs".</i>
Teacher from Italy	<i>"Colleagues are crucial in creating the right environment to share the children's growth path. Maybe there is no compatibility between a teacher and a particular child at some time, but this compatibility may be present with a colleague".</i>
Teacher from Spain	<i>"Facilitate teacher collaboration and liberate space and time for teacher group work".</i>
Teacher from Bulgaria	<i>"If closeness [with students], an individualised approach, is encouraged by the management, then everyone will strive [for it]".</i>
Teacher from Italy	<i>"The director demonstrates availability, trust and ability to listen to the teachers, he takes [teachers'] opinions into account, values and supports their role and that of the other professionals involved in teaching and extra-curricular activities".</i>
Teacher from Bulgaria	<i>"Teachers need to continuously improve their qualifications and exchange good practices with other teachers".</i>
Teacher from Lithuania	<i>"[There are] too few pupil support specialists; more and more special needs children are coming in, and the number of posts remains the same".</i>
Teacher from Portugal	<i>"Public administration must [...] value teachers' careers, have long term goals for education and not change educational goals so frequently".</i>
Teacher from Poland	<i>"I firmly believe that if the purpose of observation is to develop the teacher and improve his or her educational practice, which translates into student well-being, then such activities should become standard in our school."</i>
Teacher from Bulgaria	<i>"Sharing impressions, pedagogical experiences and methods of teaching and behaviour management in the classroom enriches professional tools and stimulates the desire to try new different approaches in order to improve work with students".</i>
Teacher from Poland	<i>"This [observation] not only concerns learning new working methods or obtaining practical tips regarding my teaching practice, but above all, a different view of the relationship with the student and its impact on the learning process".</i>
Teacher from Italy	<i>"Observation is one of the privileged tools that allows us to know what happens in the classroom, [...] to acquire greater awareness of the behaviours and attitudes of us teachers and students and of the close interaction between the former and the latter".</i>

Annex II: Methodological dossiers

Appendix 1 → [Interviews with families](#)

Appendix 2 → [Interviews with stakeholders & policymakers](#)

Appendix 3 → [Photovoice NEETS](#)

Appendix 4 → [Focus Groups](#)

Appendix 5 → [Teaching observations](#)

Annex III: Supporting Images

Figure 1: General methodological collaborative process for tool development and co-creation

Figure 2: Cloud of family perceptions of schools

What would you say to someone...?

Without education and work, a person is doomed to failure and a hard life with constant humiliations. (Female, Poland 2)	Seek help from parents, teachers, head teacher. And from supportive friends (Male, Bulgaria 1).
"Find someone with whom you don't feel lonely and who will accompany you".	Education is necessary (female, Lithuania 2).
There is always an alternative way, that often forcing things to go your way doesn't work and that maybe a pause is enough to realise what might be the right thing to do. (Italy 2)	"Have the courage to ask for help for any problem from a friend, or even from your mother, people who love you will understand you, they won't judge you. (female, Italy 3)
You should never write a person off, even if he is very unhappy, even if he refuses help, it doesn't mean that he doesn't want it.	"You are not alone"

Figure 3. Photovoice analysis

Figure 4. Photovoice portfolio, all photos available at LET's HUB

